

Quantum Hydrodynamics and the Schrodinger Equation as a Continuity Equation?

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In a quantum bound state, spatial density is given by $W(x)W(x)$, where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction, average momentum by $-i \frac{d \ln(W)}{dx}$ and average kinetic energy at x by $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W / W$. One may note that: $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W / W + V(x) = E$ is the time independent Schrodinger equation which may be solved for $W(x)$ and E without any concept of spatial density. Furthermore, one may calculate $\langle p \rangle$ and $\langle p^*p \rangle$, also without any concept of spatial density. This differs from the case of a classical fluid situation for which there is no $W(x)$. We argue that kinematics of a bound state are contained in $W(x)$ and that the Schrodinger equation is like a probability conservation hydrodynamic equation with spatial density replaced with $W(x)$ and a $V(x)W(x)$ term which we try to explain. In addition, the "conservation of momentum" hydrodynamic equation is essentially "d/dx" of the Schrodinger equation (if mass= $m=5$). This strategy differs from the general approach used throughout the literature (for example (1) and many other cases), where spatial density is taken as the starting point of a quantum hydrodynamic formalism. Spatial density is utilized in a continuity equation of the form $\frac{d}{dt} [W^*W] + \frac{d}{dx} [W^*W v] = 0$ where v is a collective velocity and d/dt the partial derivative with respect to time. We argue one only needs the concept of a wavefunction as the normalization constant of the conditional probability $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ i.e. $W(x) = \sum \text{over } p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. From this wavefunction, one may calculate $\langle p \rangle$ and $\langle p^*p \rangle$. Thus we argue that hydrodynamic type equations should apply to $W(x)$. We pointed out in (2), that $W(x)$ in fact satisfies a momentum continuity hydrodynamic equation if mass= 5 .

Conditional Probabilities

We argue that $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ ((1)) and suggest one may actually calculate averages at a point x , for example:

$$KE_{ave}(x) = [\text{Sum over } p p^*p/2m a(p) \exp(ipx)] / W(x) \quad ((2))$$

Although this is not a physical observable, $V(x)$ is also not a physical observable at a single x point alone although it is physical and not simply a math construct- its effect over dx is required or its derivative. Nevertheless, one may write a conservation equation in both classical and quantum mechanics:

$$KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((3))$$

This is in fact, the time-independent Schrodinger equation which depends only on $W(x)$. No knowledge is required of spatial density-even though it exists and is physically observable. Furthermore, one may define an average momentum at x with no concept of spatial density.

$$\langle p \rangle = [\text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx)] / W(x) = -i \frac{dW}{dx} / W \quad ((4))$$

The spatial density is something very different and is discussed in the next section. We argue that one need not associate $\langle p \rangle$ with spatial density “movement”. $\langle p \rangle$ is a function of x as is $\langle pp \rangle$ which must change to accommodate changes in $V(x)$ so that E remains constant. $W(x)$, contains dynamical information i.e.: $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. The Schrodinger equation is in fact an equation which demonstrate how $W(x,t)$ changes in time and space and displays the microscopic dynamics of the quantum system. Consider the form of the Schrodinger equation:

$$i \frac{d}{dt} W = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} [W \langle p \rangle] + V(x) W(x) \quad ((5)) \quad \text{where } \langle p \rangle = -i \frac{dW}{dx} / W$$

((5)) is very much of the form of a hydrodynamic continuity equation for probability with “spatial density” replaced with W , the extra $1/2m$ and the $V(x)W(x)$ term and the imaginary i factors. Thus, we argue that a coupling with the potential is critical for the change in W whereas such a term is absent in standard spatial density continuity equations in the literature. We argue that $V(x) = \sum_k V(k) \exp(ikx)$ so an $\exp(ikx)$ from the potential may couple with $\exp(ipx)$ from the complex probability ((1)) creating an $\exp(i(k+p)x)$ complex probability piece. Thus, probability does not change due to flow alone, it changes from hits of a stochastic potential. One may note that ((5)) holds at a point. (There actually is a physical density, so ((5)) is a hydrodynamic equation for the momentum distribution given by $W(x)$, not of physical density flow. Nevertheless, it is $W(x)$ which governs the microscopic motion of the quantum system and also gives rise to the spatial density which is $W(x)W(x)$ for a bound state.

Furthermore, as shown in (2), one may create a conservation of momentum hydrodynamic equation using $W(x)$ instead of spatial density if ones use $m=.5$. In statistical mechanics texts (3), the momentum conservation hydrodynamic equation in one dimension is written as:

$$[d/dt + u du/dx] u = 1/m F - 1/d(x) d/dx \{ d(x) \{ \langle vv \rangle - \langle u \rangle \langle u \rangle \} \} \quad ((6)) \quad d/dt = \text{partial derivative}$$

where $F(x) = -dV(x)/dx$, $u = -i dW/dx / W$ and $\langle vv \rangle = -d/dx d/dx W / W$.

If one uses $d(x) = W(x)$ in place of spatial density $d(x)$, sets $m=.5$, and d/dt to zero for the bound state, one may satisfy ((6)) as shown in (2). Thus, one does not obtain the exact result of the classical momentum equation because m is set to $.5$, but the result is very similar.

((6)), however, is equivalent to the Schrodinger equation by taking a spatial derivative, because $V(x)$ is converted into $F(x)$ and the other terms become almost equivalent to ((6)) with $m=.5$. Thus, $W(x)$ appears to follow hydrodynamical equations quite closely, although not exactly, because of the $m=.5$ issue.

This is interesting because the classical hydrodynamical equation for density conservation does not include a $V(x)W(x)$ while the Schrodinger equation does. We argued that the quantum conservation of density i.e. $W(x)$ hydrodynamical equation differs from the classical one. Why then does the classical momentum conservation hydrodynamic equation hold in quantum mechanics (for $m=.5$)? The time-independent Schrodinger equation may be written as $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx}$

$d/dx W / W + V(x)=E$ which is a conservation of energy equation. The term $-d/dx d/dx W / W$ represents $\langle p^*p \rangle$ and taking d/dx introduces terms related to $dW/dx / W$ which, in turn, is related to $\langle p \rangle$. Thus, there is a flow momentum $\langle p \rangle$ and flow kinetic energy $1/2m \langle p^*p \rangle$ at each x just as in the classical hydrodynamical situation. In addition, there is conservation of energy, so the basic physics seems present in the Schrodinger equation, although using $m=.5$ removes $1/2m$ from the Schrodinger equation. What differs in quantum mechanics is the link between the Schrodinger equation and the momentum conservation hydrodynamic equation (i.e. one simply takes d/dx if $m=.5$). In classical hydrodynamics, there is a general conservation equation for a variable X . One obtains different equations by substituting different X values such as m (probability or mass conservation) or mv , momentum conservation. It should be pointed out that classical hydrodynamics uses spatial density whereas quantum mechanics, we argue, uses the wavefunction $W(x)$ in its place.

Quantum mechanics does not start with the classical statistical mechanical general conservation equation, it begins with the Schrodinger equation in $W(x)$ which is a momentum probability distribution (albeit with complex probabilities) which describes a response to a stochastic potential $V(x)=\text{Sum over } k V(k)\exp(ikx)$.

Spatial Density

Spatial density is a physical observable in both classical hydrodynamics and quantum mechanics. In quantum mechanics, one may ask how does it arise? First, we argue that spatial density at x really exists within an interval dx . At x there is a momentum distribution given by $W(x)$, but at $x+dx$ there is a different momentum distribution because average kinetic energy = $[\text{Sum over } p a(p) p^*p/2m \exp(ipx)]/W(x)$ must change. Even though it changes because each $\exp(ipx)$ changes into $\exp(ip(x+dx))$ (like a free momentum wavefunction), we argue that stochastic potential hits are the real cause. $V(x)$ also changes from x to $x+dx$ and it must have a physical impact on $W(x)$, we argue. If one has momentum p_1 at x , somewhere in the interval x to $x+dx$ it receives a stochastic hit and changes to p_2 . Thus, one deals with product probabilities $a(p_1)\exp(ip_1 x) a(p_2)\exp(ip_2 x)$ when calculating density within a region dx . Given that this is a stochastic process, it is not so clear that it is associated with an average velocity. $W(x)$ exists at a point x , so one may calculate averages at this point, but it is not clear that an ensemble average of product probabilities used to calculate spatial density may be meaningfully associated with specific flow. One may of course write various mathematical equations utilizing density instead of $W(x)$, but we try to focus on $W(x)$ and its relationship to microscopic motion at a point. From x to $x+dx$, matters are complicated, but at $x+dx$, there are new averages which may be calculated, although it may be noted that these averages are linked to conditional probabilities $P(p/x)$ e.g. $KE_{ave}(x)= [\text{Sum over } p p^*p/2m a(p) \exp(ipx)]/W(x)$. One may also use $f(p) P(p/x)P(x)$ to calculate an average. This is equivalent to: $f(p) W(x) a(p)\exp(ipx)$ showing again the double hits. Trying to apply classical hydrodynamics to this situation seems to bypass the idea that the wavefunction represents a momentum distribution which interacts physically with a potential and so hydrodynamical equations applied to $W(x)$ may be more closely linked to physical motion (which is complicated).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue that the Schrodinger equation has the form of a density conservation hydrodynamic equation using $W(x)$ in place of the density $W^*(x)W(x)$. Furthermore, $W(x)$ also satisfies a momentum conservation hydrodynamic equation if $m=.5$ as shown in (2) which is essentially equivalent to taking d/dx of the Schrodinger equation.

The Schrodinger equation has a $V(x)W(x)$ term, thus $W(x)$, the momentum distribution, changes not only because of velocity flow $d/dx [W u]$, but also due to the coupling with a stochastic potential $V(x)=\text{Sum over } k V(k) \exp(ikx)$ which may combine with $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ terms of $W(x)$. Thus, there are two ways for $W(x)$ in the conservation of probability hydrodynamic equation (i.e. Schrodinger equation) to change.

References

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